

THE EFFECT OF BALANCE TRAINING PERFORMED WITH STROBOSCOPIC GLASSES ON REACTION TIME IN INDIVIDUALS WITH MULTIPLE SCLEROSIS: A CASE SERIES

STROBOSKOPIK GÖZLÜK İLE UYGULANAN DENGE EĞİTİMİNİN MULTİPL SKLEROZLU BİREYLERDE REAKSİYON SÜRESİNE ETKİSİ: BİR OLGU SERİSİ

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to descriptively examine changes in upper and lower extremity reaction times in individuals with MS. This descriptive case series included four female individuals diagnosed with relapsing–remitting multiple sclerosis (RRMS). Participants completed a static and dynamic balance exercise program performed with stroboscopic glasses over eight weeks, consisting of sixteen sessions. Upper and lower extremity reaction times were assessed using a computer-based system based on the Simple Visual Reaction Time (SVRT) protocol. Measurements were obtained before and after the intervention, and minimum, maximum, and mean reaction times were recorded. After the intervention, lower extremity reaction times decreased in all individuals, and the direction of individual change was consistent. The arithmetic mean reaction time decreased from 1488 ms at the pre-intervention assessment to 1100 ms at the post-intervention assessment ($\approx 26\%$ reduction). Individual changes in upper extremity reaction times showed a heterogeneous pattern. Reaction time decreased in three individuals; in these individuals, the arithmetic mean reaction time decreased from 576 ms pre-intervention to 386 ms post-intervention ($\approx 33\%$ reduction). In one individual, reaction time increased by approximately 17% following the intervention. Although not generalizable and unsuitable for causal inference, this case series provides preliminary evidence of limb-specific reaction time changes that may inform future controlled studies in individuals with MS.

Keywords: Multiple sclerosis, reaction time, balance training, stroboscopic glasses

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INTRODUCTION

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is defined as a chronic neurological disorder characterized by demyelination and axonal damage in the central nervous system, with both inflammatory and neurodegenerative processes playing a role.¹ Lesions occurring in the brain and spinal cord in MS are reported to affect motor, sensory, and cognitive functions.¹ These impairments are associated with a decline in daily living activities and functional independence.² MS is considered a significant neurological condition that frequently emerges in young adulthood and can progress to long-term disability over time.²

Individuals with MS frequently experience deficits in attention, executive functions, and particularly in information processing speed, which may result in delayed motor responses and slower reactions to environmental stimuli.³ Reaction time is considered a key performance indicator that reflects the integrated function of cognitive and motor systems, encompassing the time elapsed from the perception of a stimulus to the initiation of a motor response.⁴ Previous studies have reported that individuals with MS exhibit prolonged reaction times, which have been associated with slower cognitive processing speeds.⁵ Moreover, this process involves not only cognitive processing but also the organization and initiation of the motor response.⁴ Prolonged reaction time is considered a potential functional indicator related to balance and mobility.⁶

Rehabilitation approaches aiming to improve balance and gait performance in individuals with MS have been shown to positively influence postural control and functional mobility.⁷ Among these approaches, stroboscopic visual restriction has gained attention as a method that challenges sensory systems by intermittently limiting visual input.⁸ This technique seeks to enhance proprioceptive and vestibular system engagement by restricting visual access intermittently, thereby promoting improved balance and motor control.⁸ Studies conducted with MS populations have demonstrated short-term improvements in information processing time and static balance following the use of this technique.⁸

Reaction time is a clinical performance indicator reflecting the integrity of cognitive processing speed and motor response organization in Multiple Sclerosis. Conduction slowing secondary to demyelination and axonal damage can affect central information processing mechanisms, leading to prolonged reaction time.^{1,9} This prolongation is associated with attentional capacity, information processing speed, and postural response timing, and holds clinical significance in terms of fall risk and functional movement safety.^{10,11}

In the literature, upper extremity reaction time and lower extremity reaction time have generally been investigated separately in individuals with MS.^{6,12} However, studies evaluating both upper and lower extremity reaction times concurrently in the same individuals remain limited. The aim of this study is to investigate changes in upper and lower extremity reaction times in individuals with MS following balance training with stroboscopic glasses.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Participants

This study was designed as a descriptive case series examining changes in upper and lower extremity reaction times in individuals diagnosed with MS following balance training performed with stroboscopic glasses. Four individuals ($n = 4$) who were diagnosed with MS according to the McDonald 2017 criteria, aged between 18 and 65 years, with Expanded Disability Status Scale (EDSS) scores ranging from 2.5 to 4.5, and who scored ≥ 24 on the Standardized Mini-Mental Test administered to assess cognitive status were included in the study. Individuals who had not experienced a relapse within the previous three months, who did not present with severe spasticity in the major muscle groups of the upper and lower extremities (Modified Ashworth Scale ≤ 2), and who completed the balance exercise program performed with stroboscopic glasses were enrolled.

Individuals with severe visual or hearing impairments, medication changes within the previous three months, ongoing participation in a regular physiotherapy/rehabilitation program, a history of concomitant severe neurological, orthopedic, or vestibular disorders, contractures limiting exercise participation, or a history of epileptic seizures or vertigo within the past six months were excluded from the study.

First, the participants' sociodemographic data were recorded; reaction time was assessed before the intervention and at the end of the intervention. Upper and lower extremity reaction times were measured using a computer-based (Python), performance-based objective assessment system designed on the basis of the Simple Visual Reaction Time (SVRT) protocol, whose validity has been reported in the literature.¹³ Participants were instructed to produce a motor response as quickly as possible to the visual stimulus presented on the screen, and reaction times were recorded in milliseconds (ms). Upper and lower extremity measurements were administered as separate protocols. The type of stimulus, stimulus presentation duration, and measurement software were kept constant for both protocols. In upper extremity measurements, participants responded by pressing any key on the keyboard following the visual stimulus. In lower extremity measurements, participants were asked to respond by pressing, with their actively used foot, on an external keyboard surface placed on the floor and wirelessly integrated with the computer while standing.

The SVRT task was structured by taking into account trial numbers and inter-stimulus intervals commonly used in reaction time studies, and task duration was kept constant.¹³ During the task, visual stimuli were presented at random intervals, and short rest periods were provided between upper and lower extremity assessments when necessary. For each individual, minimum, maximum, and mean reaction times, as well as the total number of trials, were recorded. Measurements were conducted in a quiet environment, with appropriate posture ensured—seated for upper extremity assessments and standing for lower extremity assessments.

Intervention Program

Participants underwent a balance training program with stroboscopic visual restriction for eight weeks, twice weekly, totaling 16 sessions. Each session lasted approximately 45 minutes and consisted of warm-up, static balance exercises, dynamic balance exercises, and cool-down phases. Exercise planning considered fatigue levels in individuals with multiple sclerosis, and standardized rest intervals were provided when necessary.

The intervention utilized Senaptec Strobe® (Senaptec LLC, USA) stroboscopic glasses equipped with a liquid crystal lens system. The system operates on a synchronized binocular and temporally intermittent occlusion principle, in which both lenses alternate simultaneously between transparent and opaque phases. The device includes eight levels of difficulty (Level 1–8). As the level increases, the duration of the transparent phase shortens, thereby reducing the temporal availability of visual information. Through this configuration, visual feedback was progressively restricted, aiming to activate sensory reweighting mechanisms during postural control.

Frequency levels were applied according to a gradual progression principle from lower to higher levels. Two consecutive levels were used in each session (e.g., 1–2, followed by 2–3 in the subsequent session), and the participant's ability to perform the exercises safely and stably without developing compensatory strategies was accepted as the criterion for progression to the next level. By the end of the intervention period, all participants had experienced all eight levels.

The balance training program was structured to include both static and dynamic components. Static exercises consisted of nine tasks involving standing in different foot positions and weight shifting on stable and unstable surfaces. Dynamic exercises comprised ten activities, including walking in different directions, tandem walking, step ascent and descent, jumping, and functional transitions. Exercise difficulty was progressively increased according to individual performance.

Analysis

Intra-individual changes were evaluated at a descriptive level, and no statistical inference was performed.

RESULTS

The basic descriptive characteristics of the participants are presented in Table 1. Comparison of pre- and post-intervention assessments showed a reduction in lower extremity reaction times in all four individuals (Table 2). On an individual basis, although the magnitude of change in lower extremity reaction time varied among participants, the direction of change was consistently toward a decrease in all individuals. In contrast, upper extremity reaction times displayed a more variable pattern. Three participants exhibited decreased reaction times following the intervention, whereas one participant demonstrated an increase (Table 3). Changes in upper extremity reaction times were found to exhibit a more variable pattern across individuals compared with those observed in the lower extremity. This heterogeneous pattern of change may be related to the inter-individual variability in motor involvement

in MS, differences in baseline performance levels, and the indirect effects of the intervention on the upper extremity.

Table 1: Basic descriptive characteristics of the participants. EDSS: Expanded Disability Status Scale, BMI: Body Mass Index

ID	Age (years)	Gender	Height (cm)	Weight (kg)	BMI (kg/m ²)	EDSS
P1	56	Female	170	54	18.7	3.5
P2	40	Female	168	67	23.7	2.5
P3	54	Female	154	55	23.2	4
P4	65	Female	160	59	23.0	4

Table 2: Lower extremity reaction times (ms). RT: reaction time; Δ RT: difference between post- and pre-intervention measurements (Post–Pre, ms). Negative values indicate a reduction in reaction time. * Indicates a positive trend without statistical significance.

ID	Mean RT (Pre)	Mean RT (Post)	Δ RT (Post–Pre)
P1	1933.53	1122	*-811.53
P2	1322.07	1277.3	*-44.77
P3	1107.32	934.15	*-173.17
P4	1590.26	1065.22	*-525.04

Table 3: Upper extremity reaction times (ms). RT: reaction time; Δ RT: difference between post- and pre-intervention measurements (Post–Pre, ms). Negative values indicate a reduction in reaction time. * Indicates a positive trend without statistical significance.

ID	Mean RT (Pre)	Mean RT (Post)	Δ RT (Post–Pre)
P1	472.82	417.06	*-55.76
P2	811.73	515.26	*-296.47
P3	442.58	295.43	*-147.15
P4	355.7	415.58	59.88

DISCUSSION

In this study, changes in upper and lower extremity reaction times in individuals with MS following balance training performed with stroboscopic glasses were examined at a descriptive level. The findings indicate a consistent trend toward shortening of lower extremity reaction times in all

individuals, whereas a more variable pattern was observed in upper extremity reaction times across participants.

The uniform reduction in lower extremity reaction times across all individuals is noteworthy. The decrease in mean lower extremity reaction time from 1488 ms prior to the intervention to 1100 ms after the intervention corresponds to an approximate improvement of 26%. This consistent pattern of change may be attributed to the close relationship between balance exercises and lower extremity motor control, postural stability, and sensorimotor integration processes specific to the lower extremities. In exercise environments where visual input is restricted using stroboscopic glasses, individuals become more reliant on proprioceptive and vestibular inputs; this shift has been reported in the literature to have a pronounced effect on both reflexive and voluntary responses of the lower extremities.⁸

Inter-individual variability was more pronounced in upper extremity reaction times. While three individuals demonstrated a reduction in reaction time, with the mean reaction time in these individuals decreasing from 576 ms to 386 ms—representing an approximate improvement of 33%—one individual exhibited an increase in reaction time of approximately 17%. This heterogeneous pattern may be related to the variable distribution of motor system involvement among individuals with MS and to the fact that motor control processes of the upper extremities involve different neurophysiological mechanisms compared with those of the lower extremities. The literature reports that upper extremity motor performance in MS may present a more variable clinical profile across individuals.^{2,3}

The findings of this study are not generalizable due to the small sample size and the descriptive case series design. Nevertheless, the identification of extremity-specific patterns of change provides preliminary descriptive data that may contribute to a better understanding of the potential associations between balance exercises incorporating stroboscopic visual restriction and sensorimotor performance in individuals with MS. In this context, a study with a larger sample size and a controlled design is currently being conducted by the research team.

CONCLUSION

In this case series, extremity-specific patterns of change in reaction time were observed in individuals with multiple sclerosis following balance training performed with stroboscopic glasses. While a consistent reduction in lower extremity reaction times was observed in all individuals, marked inter-individual variability was noted in upper extremity reaction times. The findings suggest that balance exercises involving stroboscopic restriction of visual input may be associated with sensorimotor performance outcomes; however, the data should be interpreted at a descriptive level. Due to the small sample size and the case series design, the results are not generalizable; nevertheless, the identification of extremity-specific patterns of change provides preliminary descriptive information that may contribute to the limited literature in this field.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

FINANCIAL DISCLOSURE

None.

ETHICAL STATEMENT

All participants were provided with detailed information about the study, and written informed consent was obtained on a voluntary basis. The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. Ethical approval was obtained for the study, and the necessary permissions were secured from the relevant institution to conduct the research.

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